

To Assessing the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice regarding Food Labelling among students of DAVV”

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the frequency of reading food labels and to compare the knowledge, attitude and practice of reading the food label among students of DAVV. In this study, the purposive random sampling technique was used to collect the data from 68 volunteers aged 17- 25 years who were asked to complete an online questionnaire containing fifteen questions. Percentage analysis applied to the study data. The results show that only 88% of the total participants had read food labels, 27% of them is looking for the Protein content on the nutritional fact, 79.4% of them are aware of the sign ages mention on the food label, 52.9% check the expiry date, 38.2% are cross-checking the weight of the product & 66.2% are following the instruction mentioned on the label. There was an association between education level and knowledge of food label reading. But the consumer's education level was significantly associated with the frequency of food label reading. The study showed that the total participants frequently read the food labels. 17% of the participants stated that they buy the food products without labels and it was found that only 50% of the total participants don't believe whatever is written on the food label. Participants of this study had a low level of knowledge regarding the nutrition information that was provided on the food label. Although there is a high level of awareness regarding the food labelling among the students of DAVV.

Introduction

Youths are the potential buyers of the future, the United Nations defines 'youth' as persons aged between 15 and 24. However, this definition is flexible. According to the World Youth Report (2018), there are 1.2 billion young people aged 15 to 24 years, accounting for 16 per cent of the global population (WHO 2011). A potential buyer is one who has knowledge about the contents of the product before buying it. The term

Knowledge is 'information given meaning and integrated with other contents of understanding' (Bates, 2005). Trends are changing toward healthier and wellness food has also led to consumer demand for "more detailed, accurate, and accessible" nutritional information on packaged food (Abbott, 1997). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), food labelling includes "any written, printed or graphic matter that is present on the label, accompanies the food, including

that for the purpose of promoting its sale or disposal. Consequently, nation-states across the globe have come out with legal regulations which require mandatory nutrition labelling of packaged food products. These labelling regulations essentially reflect a response to consumers' rights to know the content and nutrition of a particular food product. The objective of these regulations is to provide consistent, understandable, and usable labels that can help consumers make informed and healthier food choices (Nayga, 1966). Most legal regulations concerning food product labelling are conceived and implemented on the basic premise that the dissemination of information in greater quantities and details will facilitate consumers in making better brand choices decision (McCullough and Best 1980). Compliance with any legal regulations, in this case, mandatory food labelling, has a cost attached to it, which either the food company has to bear leading to a lowering of its competitive advantage or is passed on to the customer making the food product costlier. The expenditure on labelling will be of use only if consumers are aware of and are able to understand, comprehend and make their purchase decision based

partially on the information given on the label. Consumer awareness refers to the individual understanding of their rights as a consumer concerning available products and services that begin marketed or sold. The concept of consumer awareness involves four categories including safety, choice, information and right to be heard. Food product labelling has become a popular policy tool in learning how to apply nutrition information in a practical way. The nutrition information on food labels can help consumers to choose healthier food, many studies in the context of industrialized nations indicate significant demographic and socio-economic differences with regard to consumer awareness and the use of information provided on food labels (Food Marketing Institute, 1989; Bender and Derby, 1992; Wandel, 1997). For example, Wandel (1995) shows that women, the highly educated and those who are on special diets, tend to read the food labels to a greater extent than others (c.f, Wandel, 1997). Many investigators have also found that the interest in reading the food labels increases with age up to the mid-fifties, and thereafter it declines. The typical food label reader is reported to be a middle-aged woman with high

education (Wandel, 1995).

The food processing industry is one of the largest in India. It is ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. Food processing industry is of enormous significance for India's development because it has linked up the economy, industry and agriculture in India (Sethassociates.com). The global packaged food market size was valued at \$1,925.7 billion in 2020 and is projected to reach \$3,407.2 billion by 2030, registering a CAGR (Compound annual growth rate) of 5.2% from 2021 to 2030. The meat poultry and seafood segment were the highest contributor to the packaged food market in 2020 and is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 4.8% during the forecast period. The Indian food and beverage packaging market was valued at USD\$ 33.22 billion in 2020, and it is expected to reach USD\$ 156.25 billion by 2026, registering a CAGR of 29.88% during the forecast period (2021-2026). India has seen sustainable packaging growth in Food & Beverage due to the increase in packaged food consumption and awareness, and demand for quality products (www.mordorintelligence.com). Riding high on the retail industry's wave of growth in India is the label industry,

which has grown by almost more than 25% in the last four years. It is roughly Rs 12-15 billion industry and the label stock production has already crossed half a billion square meters per annum.

Types of labels include wet glue paper labels, pressure sensitive labels, thermal transfer label, flexible wrap around labels and shrink sleeves etc.

Labelling requirements according to FSSAI

: General Requirements

Every pre-packaged food shall carry a label containing information as required here under unless otherwise provided, namely, —

The particulars of declaration required under these Regulations to be specified on the label shall be in English or Hindi in Devanagari script: Provided that nothing herein contained shall prevent the use of any other language in addition to the language required under this regulation.

Pre-packaged food shall not be described or presented on any label or in any labelling manner that is false, misleading or deceptive or is likely to create an erroneous impression regarding its character in any respect;

Label in pre-packaged foods shall be applied in such a manner that they will not become separated from the

container; Contents on the label shall be clear, prominent, indelible and readily legible by the consumer under normal conditions of purchase and use;

Where the container is covered by a wrapper, the wrapper shall carry the necessary information or the label on the container shall be readily legible through the outer wrapper and not obscured by it;

Labelling of Pre-packaged Foods

In addition to the General Labelling requirements specified in 1.1.1 above every package of food shall carry the following information on the label, namely, —

The Name of Food: The name of the food shall include trade name or description of food contained in the package.

List of Ingredients: Except for single ingredient foods, a list of ingredients shall be declared on the label in the following manner: —

The list of ingredients shall contain an appropriate title, such as the term “Ingredients”;

The name of Ingredients used in the product shall be listed in descending order of their composition by weight or

volume, as the case may be, at the time of its manufacture;

Nutritional information – Nutritional Information or nutritional facts per 100 gm or 100ml or per serving of the product shall be given on the label containing the following: —

energy value in kcal;

the amounts of protein, carbohydrate (specify quantity of sugar) and fat in gram (g) or ml;

the amount of any other nutrient for which a nutrition or health claim is made:

Provided that where a claim is made regarding the amount or type of fatty acids or the amount of cholesterol, the amount of saturated fatty acids, monounsaturated fatty acids and polyunsaturated fatty acids in gram (g) and cholesterol in milligram (mg) shall be declared, and the amount of trans fatty acid in gram (g) shall be declared in addition to the other requirement stipulated above; Wherever, numerical information on vitamins and minerals is declared, it shall be expressed in metric units; Where the nutrition declaration is made per serving, the amount in gram (g) or millilitre (ml) shall be included for reference beside the serving measure;

Declaration regarding Veg or Non veg –

Every package of “non-Vegetarian” food shall bear a declaration to this effect made by a symbol and colour code as stipulated below to indicate that the product is Non- Vegetarian Food. The symbol shall consist of a brown colour filled circle having a diameter not less than the minimum size specified in the Table mentioned in the regulation inside a square with brown outline having sides double the diameter of the . Declaration regarding Food Additives-

For food additives falling in the respective classes and appearing in lists of food additives permitted for use in foods generally, the following class titles shall be used together with the specific names or recognized international numerical identifications: Acidity Regulator, Acids, Anticaking Agent, Antifoaming Agent, Antioxidant, Bulking Agent, Colour, Colour Retention Agent, Emulsifier, Emulsifying Salt, Firming Agent, Flour Treatment Agent, Flavour Enhancer, Foaming Agent, Gelling Agent, Glazing Agent, Humectant, Preservative, Propellant, Raising Agent, Stabilizer, Sweetener, Thickener

Addition of colours and/or Flavours— (a) Extraneous addition of colouring matter to be mentioned on the label – Where an extraneous colouring matter has been added to any article of food, there shall be displayed one of the following statements in capital letters, just beneath the list of the ingredients on the

label attached to any package of food so coloured, namely:

Aims and Objectives:

The study is conducted on the students to understand the awareness level regarding food labelling because youth are potential buyer of the future. The study has following implications To find out the knowledge level of youth regarding Nutritional labels, Its importance for health and significance of difference signages they're on packets.To find out the practices followed by youth for nutritional labels, MRP, QR code, Food declaration and food and nutritional labels before buying food products.

To find out the youth attitudes towards buying food without food labelling.

METHODOLOGY

To follow the research, the first and most important thing is to identify the research problem. A researcher can choose a topic according to his/her liking and pursue his/her interest to the utmost limit. The selection of a topic is a commitment of one's time and effort in a particular direction.The main aim of the research is to find out the truth which is being

hidden and which has not been discovered yet. So, in the present study entitled *“To Assessing the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice regarding Food Labelling among students of DAVV”*, the methodology of the present study is preceded under the following heads:

- Design of research process and methodology
- Objectives of the study
- Working definitions
- Research Design
- Tools and Techniques
- Statistical Analysis

Objectives of the study

To find out the knowledge level of youth regarding Nutritional labels, Its importance for health and significance of different signages their on packets.

To find out the practices followed by youth for nutritional labels, MRP, Expiry date, QR code, Food declaration and food and nutritional labels before buying food products.

To find out the youth attitudes towards buying food without food labelling.

Working Definitions

Assess: To judge or decide the amount, value, quality, or importance of something.

Knowledge: Understanding of or information about a subject that get by experience or study, either known by one person or by people generally.

Food labelling: Food label is any tag, brand, mark, pictorial or other descriptive matter, written, printed, stencilled, marked, embossed or impressed on, or attached to, a container of food or food product.

Attitude: An attitude is a positive, negative, or mixed evaluation of an object expressed at some level of intensity.

Practice: Practice means doing something regularly in order to be able to do it better.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Sample designing: Sample designing is a very important aspect of the scientific research methodology. A sample is a finite part of a statistical population whose properties are studied to gain information about the whole (Webster, 1985). When the group is taken as a representative of the whole, the study is called the sampling technique. The whole group from which the sample has been drawn is technically known as inverse or population and the group

selected for the study is known as 'Sample'. When the sample is good, it represents the population and certain things can be predicted. About the population from which it was drawn. This is known as statistical inference. Taking into consideration all these points following sample design has been propagated systematically.

Sampling techniques: In the present study Purposive random sampling technique was used for the sample selection.

Selection criteria: The area of the research is pre-decided which is the DAVV Campus because the same need to be students aged between 17-25 years. The minimum requirements for selection are 1. Should have Smartphone and 2. Internet connection enables them to fill out the online questionnaire. The form link is shared with them through their e-mail address and asked to share the link with their classmates. A total of 68 participants gave their responses.

Tools and Techniques:

The research was conducted as a survey in DAVV Indore, India. The study included student studying in the University. Respondents were

approached at random as they exited from their Respective Departments. Consent was taken from respondents before undertaking the study. A Purposive random sampling technique was used to collect the information from 68 volunteers for this study. Data were collected through a modified questionnaire developed based on questionnaires used reliably in previous studies. The questionnaire was administered to respondents, and assessed the use and understanding of food labels. It consisted of 7 sections. Section 1 assessed the demographic characteristics of the respondent. Section 2 examined respondent's knowledge whether the food product carries a nutritional label. If their response is Yes, they can continue with Section 3, If no they redirected to the Submit form Menu. In Section 3,4,5 & 6 the main questions asked related to the food labelling which includes some direct questions and some picture question (like food declaration symbols). Section 7 include rating out of 5 to this survey which is optional section. The study participants were male or female Students aged between 17-25 years of age who could able to read and understand English

Discussion

This study has revealed that knowledge, attitude and Practice of pre-packaged food labelling information were high among the students of DAVV, Indore. It was also observed that a maximum number of the total respondents frequently read the food labels. Similar studies have reported that the respondents with a high level of education are reading food labels more frequently. Our findings showed that the education level of the respondents was not associated with their knowledge about food labels. However, the education level of the respondents was associated with the frequency of food label reading. Although the education level of the consumers was high, they have enough knowledge level to interpret the food label. The frequency of reading food labels by the students was specific to the contents mentioned on the food label. They were able to interpret the food label to a certain extent and thus were able to choose the food products according to their needs. Earlier research studies done in India and other countries have found that there was a direct relationship between the education level of consumers and their habit of

checking food labels. Robert S D, Chandran A et al. (2017), the results from this study indicated that the awareness level among the consumers related to the food labelling was low but respondents who have a college degree or Studying in the college have read the food label more frequently and the awareness level amongst them was high. Another study was done by Surendran S, Terrence Madhujith et al. (2015), in their study ninety-two per cent of the consumers are aware of the information provided on the food labels. They assign very high importance to information about the expiry date and manufacture, 'ingredients' contained in packaged foods, nutritional information, instructions for use, health warnings and health claims. The results provide a clear indication that label information is generally gendered insensitive. Though, their study shows significance with age, level of education, income level and occupation of the respondents.

Conclusion

Consumption of packaged food items in Groceries stores has grown tremendously in the recent past decades. Food labelling enables consumers to make informed decisions when

purchasing and consuming food products. Despite this, the issue of consumer awareness about the usage of food labelling information has attracted little attention among consumers in developing countries. In this regard, the present study has attempted to analyse the Knowledge, Attitude and practice regarding Food Labelling of Students. In the present study, the sample size was 68 and most numbers of the participants are Males (n=44) ranging the age from 17 to 25 years most of them were from the Undergraduate level and some of them are from the Postgraduate level. The Female participants were n=24 ranging the age from 17 to 25 years most of them were from the Undergraduate level and some of them are from the Postgraduate level. Most numbers of the participants are checking the Food labelling in some either they looking for the price, quantity and nutritional label. Most numbers of the participants are checking for the Protein content followed by Total fat, Sodium Content and Fat of the food packet from the nutritional label section. There are some image-related questions to check if the respondents are aware of what the image signifies. Images like Barcode, QrCode, Food declaration (Green/Brown) and Garbage Can and the

awareness level of the participants was High related to these Signages. There is also a positive response in relation to the MRP which means the respondents are always checking the price of the food product before purchasing it. There is also a lack of cross-checking the weight of the pre-packaged food amongst the respondents which means the least number of the respondents are cross-checking the weight of the food product and most of them are believed what quantity is mentioned on the food label. Believing what is mentioned in the food product labelling among the respondent is very low which means respondents didn't believe what was mentioned in the food product labelling which is a good thing also there are respondents who believed what was mentioned in the food product labelling like the quantity, nutritional facts and what product is guaranteed. A maximum number of the participants are checking the expiry date, there are also the participants who are not checking the expiry date but their number is less but they should check the expiry date otherwise the product is hazardous to the health. It is concluded that the awareness level regarding food labelling is high amongst the students of DAVV.

References

1. Amal Alshukri & Safia Elramli & Hana Albkoush (2020) "Study of knowledge, attitude and awareness of the information of food labeling among consumers in Tripoli municipality Libya" Link: - shorturl.at/IHRW1
2. Amanda J Daley, Eleanor McGee, Sue Bayliss, April Coombe, Helen M Parretti (2019) Effects of physical activity calorie equivalent food labelling to reduce food selection and consumption: systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled studies. Link: - shorturl.at/ajFP8
3. Christopher P F Marinangeli, Scott V Harding, Andrea J Glenn, Laura Chiavaroli, Andreea Zurbau, David J A Jenkins, Cyril W C Kendall, Kevin B Miller, John L Sievenpiper(2020) Destigmatizing Carbohydrate with Food Labeling: The Use of Non-Mandatory Labelling to Highlight Quality Carbohydrate Foods Link: - shorturl.at/guwCH
4. Daniela Martini, Davide Menozzi(2021) Food Labeling: Analysis, Understanding, and Perception Link: - shorturl.at/aqwFS
5. Emma Tonkin a, Annabelle M Wilson a, John Coveney b, Samantha B Meyer c, Julie Henderson d, Dean McCullum e, Trevor Webb f, Paul R Ward a(2015) Consumers respond to a model for (re)building consumer trust in the food system Link: - shorturl.at/vAPQT
6. James Osei Mensah, Robert Aidoo(2012) Use and Understanding of Food Label Information and Effect on their Purchasing Decision in Ghana; a Case Study of Kumasi Metropolis Link: - shorturl.at/ivAV4
7. Jaya Surya Kumari Manthena, K. Mythili, V. Rao (2012) Current scenario of health and nutrition claims on food labels in India : a study of pre-packaged food Link: - shorturl.at/anpL1
8. Jessica Packer, Simon J Russell, Deborah Ridout, Steven Hope, Anne Conolly, Curtis Jessop, Oliver J Robinson, Sandro T Stoffel, Russell M Viner, Helen Croker (2021) Assessing the Effectiveness of Front of Pack Labels: Findings from an Online Randomised- Controlled Experiment in a Representative British Sample. Link: - shorturl.at/nBJTW
9. Klaus G Grunert, Josephine M Wills, Laura Fernández-Celemín(2010) Nutrition knowledge, and use and understanding of nutrition information on food labels among consumers in the UK Link: - shorturl.at/cizAC
10. Klazine Van der Horst, Tamara Bucher, Kerith Duncanson, Beatrice Murawski, David Labbe (2019) Consumer Understanding, Perception and Interpretation of Serving Size Information on Food Labels: A Scoping Review Link: - shorturl.at/knFRU
11. Komeela Cannoosamy, Prity Pugo Gunsam, Rajesh Jeewon(2014) Consumer Knowledge and Attitudes Toward Nutritional Labels Link: - shorturl.at/htADV
Link: - shorturl.at/ahtuT
12. M Cecchini, L Warin (2015) Impact of food labelling systems on food choices and eating behaviours: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized studies Link: - shorturl.at/uAEM5